

Why do poverty traps exist at the country and household levels? How are the two different levels of poverty traps related? What policy (or policies) would you suggest to tackle the coexistence of country-level and household-level poverty traps?

(ES30035: Coursework)

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SECTION A

Q1.

1. Introduction

Between 1960 and 2023, the Dominican Republic's GDP per capita rose from \$204 to \$10,716, in the same time, Haiti's modestly increased from \$70 to \$1,693 (World Bank, 2024). This economic stagnation is evident in Haiti's social indicators: as of 2017, only 31% of the population had completed lower secondary education compared to nearly 61.4% in the Dominican Republic, and life expectancy now stands at 64 years versus 74 in the Dominican Republic. As these two nations share an island, this divergence is not merely a result of geography, but reflects deeper, self-reinforcing cycles known as poverty traps. Analysing the mechanisms of poverty traps is critical in understanding how economic disparities manifest both across nations and within them. After modelling their causes, this essay will explore how poverty traps at the household and country level are mutually reinforcing, with national-level stagnation exacerbating barriers to upward mobility, and widespread household poverty constraining economic growth and development. With that in mind, the essay investigates how a Big-Push intervention could simultaneously address both types of poverty trap, aiming to disrupt the dynamics that perpetuate poverty at both levels.

2. The Existence of Poverty Traps

2.1 National Poverty Traps

At the national level, a poverty trap emerges when sectors lack coordination in adopting more productive technologies. When deciding whether to invest, individual firms often overlook the broader benefits that arise from widespread collective adoption of modern technology. This lack of coordination keeps the sector stuck in a Pareto-inefficient equilibrium, dampening economic progress.

A model economy consists of N goods and sectors, each sector producing x_i number of homogenous goods, priced at p_i (which is normalised to 1).

Production occurs using either traditional (A_{old}) or modern technology (A_{new}). Traditional technology converts one unit of labour into one unit of output, while modern technology yields $\alpha > 1$ units of output per unit of labour. Firms that adopt modern technology first gain a monopoly position.

Traditional firms operate in perfect competition, so the marginal product labour (p_i) will equal the wage rate:

$$p_i = w^t = 1$$

Since goods are homogenous, monopolies can't charge a price higher than traditional firms:

$$p_i = p^m = 1$$

Households derive utility from consuming goods, the representative utility function is given by:

$$u = \sum_i \ln(x_i)$$

Consumption expenditure is also evenly distributed, such that:

$$x_i p_i = x_i = \frac{Y}{N}$$

Adopting modern technology involves a fixed cost, requiring F units of labour to industrialise. This makes sense intuitively, implementing complex systems like automation in a car factory demands a minimum number of workers to operate and initiate production. Also, to compensate workers for the disutility of learning new skills to operate modern technology, modern firms pay a wage premium:

$$w^m = w^t + v = 1 + v \text{ (where } v > 0\text{)}$$

This means that a monopolist's profits are given by:

$$\pi = \left(1 - \frac{w^m}{\alpha}\right) \frac{Y}{N} - w^m F$$

Figure 1: Reduced Average Cost of Modern Technology

Because A_{new} is more productive than A_{old} , the cost of adoption is lower for a given number of adopters. The presence of complementarities causes average cost to decrease with the number of adopters. For example, the spillover of technical knowledge may facilitate easier machine maintenance, while a larger market for A_{new} can foster the development of more efficient and accessible supply chains.

In Figure 1, if x number of firms adopt A_{new} , complementarities become large enough such that the average cost of A_{new} falls below that of A_{old} . Monopoly profits become positive, so the remaining traditional firms would profit maximise by following suit and begin producing with A_{new} , such that average cost decreases to AC_{new} .

Figure 2: Economy with Two Equilibria

If firms fail to collectively adopt A_{new} such that the number of firms adopting modern technology is less than x , all firms either remain with or regress to traditional technology. This equilibrium, shown by point A on Figure 2, reflects an economy with comparatively low productive capacity. Without the cost advantages of modern technology, firms are unable to establish monopolistic positions, resulting in higher average costs and zero profits. Without the wage premium, households face a tighter budget constraint, limiting consumption and ultimately household utility. As GDP is comprised of total firm profit and household income, this poverty trap creates a less dynamic economy and hinders economic growth.

2.2 Household Poverty Traps

Household poverty traps emerge due to limited access to credit, which stifles opportunities for entrepreneurship. Financial institutions base their lending decisions on the perceived likelihood of repayment. In poorer economies - typically marked by high inequality and weak legal frameworks - this dynamic discourages lending to low-income households, resulting in limited business creation and stagnating wages.

In this model, individuals are distributed across three occupations. Subsistence workers use their endowment of labour to produce an output (s) and generate interest on their inherited wealth (Z) at rate r :

$$Y^S = s + (1 + r)Z$$

Industrial workers are paid a wage (w) by entrepreneurs and similarly generate interest:

$$Y^W = w + (1 + r)Z$$

Entrepreneurs produce an output (q), to do so requires an initial investment (I). To finance this investment, an entrepreneur borrows at interest rate r , using wealth as a collateral. Wealth again earns interest r ; production requires m number of industrial workers:

$$Y^E = q - mw - (1 + r)(I - Z)$$

We assume an entrepreneur's income is greater than that of a subsistence worker:

$$q - mw - (1 + r)(I + Z) > s + (1 + r)Z$$

$$q - mw - (1 + r)I > s$$

When wage level equals the subsistence output, an entrepreneur is better off than an industrial worker.

If an entrepreneur defaults, they lose their collateral. With probability λ , an entrepreneur is also arrested, loses all profits and is fined (F). Therefore, an entrepreneur repays the loan if the income from repaying is higher than when defaulting:

$$q - mw - (1 + r)(I + Z) \geq (1 - \lambda)(q - mw) + \lambda(-F)$$

A lender grants a loan conditional upon:

$$Z \geq I - \frac{\lambda(q - mw + F)}{1 + r}$$

This condition indicates that loans are granted only to sufficiently wealthy borrowers in contexts where significant and enforceable penalties deter default. Menkhoff (2012) highlights that individuals in developing economies often lack adequate collateralizable assets. This becomes increasingly detrimental when coupled with Menkhoff's (2005) findings on opaque information in risk assessments and screening, leading banks to demand higher collateral. Furthermore, developing countries often lack legal repercussions to facilitate lending, and even when laws are in place to punish defaults, poor institutions in these nations often fail to enforce them (Pistoret al., 2000). Ultimately, lack of wealth and credit market imperfections likely prevent potential borrowers in developing economies accessing credit.

These findings have significant implications for the labour market. Let \bar{w} represent the industrial wage level that equates the income of industrial workers with that of entrepreneurs. When $w = \bar{w}$, the economy experiences a muted increase in demand because fewer individuals have access to loans. Conversely, when $w = s$, there is a substantial increase in labour supply as there are many subsistence workers who become indifferent between their current work and industrial jobs. As illustrated in Figure 3, workers with minimal wealth remain trapped by low wages; a substantial demand increase is required to break this stagnation. Meanwhile, wealthier individuals enjoy high profits, facing little competition and benefiting from the low market wage. This dynamic exacerbates economic inequality.

Figure 3: Low Wage Equilibrium

2.3 Reinforcing Mechanisms

Kraay and McKenzie (2014) argue that the greatest determinant of poverty for an individual is the level of poverty at their country's level. One reason for this comes from Jalan and Ravallion's (2002) findings, investments made in poorer areas tend to be less productive, which inferably reduces profit incentives for entrepreneurs and leads to lower wage growth. Furthermore, by simply migrating to wealthier countries, individuals can often improve purchasing power and achieve higher wages. However, for poor households, migration is not a feasible solution to their poverty due to the high costs associated with relocation. Similarly to the situation with investment, poor households are unlikely to receive credit to finance migration.

This leads into the idea that both poverty traps are also mutually reinforcing, with the effects of each amplifying the other. Barajas and Steiner (2002) find that during economic downturns or with adverse expectations on economic growth, banks become more cautious in their lending practices. This caution is a logical response; if the anticipated return on investment is low, banks are less inclined to invest or lend. As a result, the lack of available credit could prevent poorer households from creating businesses, which leads to low wages. From the model in part 2.1, demand is a function of income, lower income in the economy will reduce aggregate demand. Keynes (1936) argues that private investment is in part a product of aggregate demand; insufficient demand creates a disincentive for firms to purchase productive technology. Moreover, subsequent low wage growth prevents households generating sufficient wealth to use as collateral when accessing credit. This highlights a cycle in which both poverty traps feed into each other, perpetuating economic stagnation.

3. Breaking Poverty Traps

3.1 The Big-Push

The coexistence of these poverty traps could be addressed by subsidising the adoption of productive technology.

Figure 4: Subsidisation of Modern Technology

Through subsidies, the fixed cost of adopting modern technology is reduced from F to F' . As illustrated in Figure 4, this reduction causes the modern technology curve to shift leftward. By lowering the cost of adoption, the threshold value of x decreases from x to x' , meaning that fewer firms need to invest in modern technology for it to become more profitable than traditional technology. As a result, the likelihood of coordination failure decreases, making a fully modernised economy more achievable.

With the adoption of modern technology, firms produce and sell a larger quantity of good x_i , leading to an increase in firm profits (q). This higher profitability, due to the threat of arrest, increases the value of repaying a loan more than the value of defaulting. Consequently, a borrower is more likely to repay their loan, improving the expected return on investment for banks. As a result, banks become more willing to lend, enabling households better access to credit and entrepreneurship.

Figure 5: Subsidisation and the Labour Market

For any given wage, there is a reduction in the labour supplied and an increase in labour demanded as more households transition to entrepreneurship. If these shifts are sufficiently large, Figure 5 demonstrates the subsequent increase in the equilibrium wage. Because each unit of labour is more productive, and fixed costs are reduced, firms are willing to pay a larger wage premium in order to retain their share of a diminishing labour supply.

$$q - m\bar{w} - (1 + r)(I + Z) = \bar{w} + (1 + r)Z$$

$$\bar{w} = \frac{q - (1 + r)I}{1 + m}$$

The equation above indicates that the wage level at which households are indifferent between industrial work and entrepreneurship also increases with q . Not only does technology subsidisation incentivise a widespread adoption of modern technology, but through increased access to credit, households may be able to break out of their poverty trap.

3.2 Limitations of The Big-Push

While the outcome of a Big-Push intervention appears theoretically positive, its effectiveness is greatly determined by the level of strategic market power within an industry and the quality of legal institutions (Fontenay 2004).

A firm with strategic market power is primed to influence the actions of complementary industries, making them an ideal target for subsidisation. Such a firm would benefit from the complementarities present in widespread adoption. However, after investing it becomes difficult and costly for a firm to withdraw. Therefore, if an influential firm lacks competition in their market, they may be incentivised to ‘hold-up’ firms who invest.

The latter materialised in Honduras during their development of agroexport production between 1975-1995. The large concentration of power within the processing sector of the Aguan region was abused, creating downward pressure on export crop farmers. Weak institutions failed to prevent the fraudulent accounting, theft and ghost payrolling that occurred in the monopsony processing plants, which destroyed crop values (Fontenay 2004). Attempts by farmers to process their crops elsewhere were also thwarted as the processing firm had influence over military checkpoints leaving Agua.

Conversely, this policy in the Sula region caused a much larger adoption of export crops and considerably higher employment in the farming sector. Through the introduction of government processing facilities, competition was generated in the market, and with a lower threat of hold-up, encouraged farmers to grow export crops. Importantly, this level of competition was established prior to the Big-Push, successful efforts by the processing firm to create barriers to entry in the Agua region demonstrate why competition is much more difficult to solidify after the fact.

Ultimately, a government must fully understand the ability of its institutions to ward off corporate capture and enforce private contracts, as well as the level of competition within its targeted industry. In a developing nation, institutions are often weak, and with a small economy firms are more likely to hold strategic market power. In this case, pre-emptive competition inducing measures are required to create an effective Big-Push.

4. Conclusion

Poverty traps can have devastating effects on economic growth and, consequently, the quality of life for a country's households. Addressing both types of poverty traps simultaneously may be crucial for overcoming economic stagnation, given the mutually reinforcing mechanisms present. One potential solution is the large-scale subsidisation of productive technologies, which could drive widespread adoption, boost firm profits, improve access to credit, and ultimately lead to wage growth. However, developing nations will likely need to implement competitive measures before introducing subsidies to maximise the effectiveness of this intervention.

Bibliography

- Barajas, A. and Steiner, R., 2002. Credit Stagnation in Latin America [Online]. *IMF Working Paper No. 2002/053*. Available from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3923415 [Accessed 5 December 2024].
- Basu, K., 1999. Child Labor: Cause, Consequence, and Cure, with Remarks on International Labor Standards [Online]. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 37(3), pp.1083–1119. Available from: [Accessed 3 December 2024].
- Basu, K. and Hoang Van, P., 1998. The Economics of Child Labor [Online]. *The American Economic Review*, 88(3), pp.412–427. Available from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/116842> [Accessed 2 December 2024].
- Corno, L., Hildebrandt, N. and Voena, A., 2020. Age of Marriage, Weather Shocks, and the Direction of Marriage Payments [Online]. *Econometrica*, 88(3), p.879–915. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3466455> [Accessed 3 December 2024].
- Fontenay, C.C., 2004. The Dual Role of Market Power in the Big Push: from Evidence to Theory [Online]. *Journal of Development Economics*, 75(1), pp.221–238. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2003.09.003>.
- Jalan, J. and Ravallion, M., 2002. Geographic Poverty Traps? A Micro Model of Consumption Growth in Rural China [Online]. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 17(4), pp.329–346. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.645> [Accessed 8 December 2024].
- Keynes, J.M., 1936. The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money. [Online]. *Political Science Quarterly*, 51(4). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2143949>.
- Kraay, A. and McKenzie, D., 2014. Do Poverty Traps Exist? Assessing the Evidence [Online]. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(3), pp.127–148. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.28.3.127> [Accessed 10 December 2024].
- Menkhoff, L., Neuberger, D. and Rungruxsivorn, O., 2012. Collateral and Its Substitutes in Emerging Markets' Lending [Online]. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 36(3), pp.817–834. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378426611002640> [Accessed 4 December 2024].
- Menkhoff, L., Neuberger, D. and Suwanaporn, C., 2006. Collateral-based Lending in Emerging markets: Evidence from Thailand [Online]. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 30(1), pp.1–21. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378426605000245> [Accessed 5 December 2024].

Pistor, K., Raiser, M. and Gelfer, S., 2000. Law and Finance in Transition Economies. *The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development*, 8(2), pp.325–368.

Weiner, M., 1991. *The Child and the State in India : Child Labor and Education Policy in Comparative Perspective*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

World Bank, 2024. *World Bank Open Data* [Online]. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/> [Accessed 18 November 2024].